

The protection of Cultural Landscapes

The Syrian City of Maaloula as a Case Study

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1- Historical background

1-1 The toponymy and site of Maaloula:

'Maaloula' is a word of an Aramyan origin, which means the entry or the strait; the name reflects the narrow lanes that lead to the site, and was called during the Greek era 'salouqyat al-qalamoun'. The name remained in use for a period of time in the scribes of the Greek church, and it is still preserved today by the Orthodox Romans.

The city occurs at 51 km from Damascus, on the international highway that leads to Homs. It is thought to be built for defensive purposes, as its entrance is fenced by two profound valleys or straits to the area of the third Qalamoun table. One of them is called 'the western valley', the second 'the eastern valley', whereas the main gateway to the east (the highway linking Damascus to Homs) is hovered by two elevated hillocks to the western and eastern sides.

Maaloula possesses some properties that can rarely be found in other cities. It is characterized by its location at the foot of a hill between two mountains of the Qalamoun chain, bordered by two valleys that convey to a vast plain of green. The buildings overlap and intertwine at the foot of the hill, constituting a unique architectural tissue. It is equally distinguished by its caves, famous monasteries, ancient churches, special religious days, and the Aramaic language that is still a living medium of communication there. All these attributes endow it with its uniqueness, and accounts for its religious, civilizational, and touristic importance.

ARABIC	ARAMAIC	ARABIC	ARAMAIC	ARABIC	ARAMAIC	ARABIC	ARAMAIC
ق	ܩ	ص	ܨ	خ	ܫ	ا	ܐ
ك	ܟ	ط	ܥ	ذ	ܕ	ب	ܒ
ل	ܠ	ظ	ܦ	ر	ܪ	ت	ܬ
م	ܡ	ع	ܥ	ز	ܙ	ث	ܛ
ن	ܢ	غ	ܓ	س	ܫ	ج	ܟ
ه	ܚ	ف	ܦ	ش	ܫ	ح	ܚ
و	ܘ						

Aramaic alphabet of Maaloula extracted from the book: "the Aramaic as spoken in Maaloula".

1.2 The Topography of the town of Maaloula:

The town of Maaloula is built on a hard rocky slope, and many of its locations are comparable to a steep cliff. As has been indicated above, it is surrounded by three hills forming a 'Y' shape. It is clear that this mountainous landscape dictated special architectural and constructional standards.

The ancient city of Maaloula is located on a slope, at the most elevated point above the sea level, with a height of 1428 m, the degree of the slope inclination varying from 40 to 50%, the lowest point in the ancient city reaching 1318 m above the sea level.

2- The main components of the landscapes and their most eminent aesthetic, environmental, and natural characteristics

2-1 Analysis of the surrounding environment

Due to the favorable geographic location, to the fertile agricultural lands, and abundance of water springs, the area has always been an appropriate and crucial host of settlements. Maaloula also presents a juxtaposition of relief scenes from tables to mountains, separated by two main valleys (each called a pass), one to the eastern side and the other on the western side, forming a strait and constituting the borders of the current ancient city, as well as the transit paths to the caves that were previously inhabited by archaic humans at the upper area surrounding the Monastery of Mar Sarkis.

The houses of the town are situated at the level of these mountain passes in an amphitheater shape on the body of the lofty mountain, and by its foreshore lie two towering rock walls on both its eastern and western borders. The houses blend with the texture of the mountain, both being indiscernible from each other. It is believed that the dwelling places in the city were caves within the mountain, and that the inhabitants accessed to them by ascending some stone stairs or benches, which is proved by the presence of a great number of large caves that were inhabited by the Stone Age man.

2.2 Springs and water courses

Areas around springs and water courses always attracted large human settlements since the Stone Age. Urban life developed in their proximity, having as a major activity every type of land culture, as those resources provided the required amount of water for land and animals. There are several water springs in Maaloula, all in its upper part, and flow into two main brooklets, the eastern and the western. They function through a special water system, composed of 26 Addans (a traditional measurement unit). On these water courses, norias were built to raise water. The pipes with which the mountain passes were equipped, and which carried spring water, helped setting up hammams since the Roman era, such as the

Malika (queen) hammam. They also contributed to the formation of the natural characteristics of the area and the green extensions of lands, where trees are by themselves visual horizons of green, mitigating the vehement stiffness of hills and rocky mountains, such as the towering high-rise poplar trees.

2.3 Floods and their courses

The area of Maaloula is exposed to huge floods, and throughout its history, floods have hit the town, causing numerous disasters, the oldest of which occurred around the 11th to 12th centuries, when the flood violently inundated all the Qalamoun zone, down from the high mountains, which resulted in changing the figure of Maaloula. Several floods were named after some of the victims, like Oum Najib flood in 1921, and Aziz flood in 1937.

The likelihood of flood occurrence in the future is still hovering on the area, which requires the issue to be seriously addressed to avert any threats in this regard. Floods primarily run through the eastern and western passes, where huge amounts of water aggressively overflow. But in normal conditions, water stream through pipes in the eastern and western passes, and converge with snowmelt water.

2.4 Natural components of archeological or religious character

1. Caves: they go back to prehistory and Roman and Greek periods, where some of their Greek inscriptions date back to 333-64 B.C. Other caves were used in the roman period as temples in 64-395 A.D. During the Byzantine period, some of them functioned as chapels, such as the Al-Khoury Youssef cave mentioned earlier, situated near the main entrance of the hotel, and the fresco paintings representing an eagle spreading its wings, standing for some religious rites practiced in the roman period to relief the dead.

Some of the caves were used as dwellings, some other as places of worship as we saw earlier, and another part was used for other purposes, such as the caves located at the level of the western mountain pass. The human-built basins and pipes inside the caves shows that they had other functions like pressing olive or grapes for wine industry that Maaloula was known for since ancient times.

As to man-made caves that were used as shelters of Archaic humans, their dimensions range is 5-8 x 3-4 m, the cave interior being more elevated than the entrance height.

3. Examination of the major issues that these areas are confronted with

3.1 Organizational issues and their impact on landscapes

The archeological site of Maaloula has gone through several historical eras as follows: Prehistory; Greek and Roman periods; Byzantine era; the Middle Ages; before 1965; and from 1965 till 2004. The negative impact started to become obvious since the second half of the last century. The ancient city was delimited as provided by a edict issued by the General

Directorate of monuments and museums, taking into account the eastern and western passes as natural determinants. Nevertheless, the ancient city previously reached the eastern hills towards the Monastery of Mar Thecla and the western hills towards the Court. Some of the eminent and wonderful buildings in both areas surrounding the old town are still standing.

Before the implementation of the 1965 urban master plan, this surrounding was highly in harmony with the city, of which it was viewed as being a part or an extension from all constructional, architectural and even visual aspects. This harmony has been greatly harmed due to the urban plan implementation in 1965, which complied with the law on higher-floor owners that was incompatible with the specificity of the ancient Maaloula texture. The 1965 urban plan implementation covered around 37 hectares, whereas 1998 urban master plan covered 107 hectares, Maaloula population having reached in 1994 2838 inhabitants.

3.2 Safeguard of the civilizational and historical legacy

Before any classification of the buildings and archeological sites in the city of Maaloula, we need to examine first the legal measures applied to the area. The cultural, touristic and administrative authorities highlighted the importance of the city, deeming that the areas of caves and both eastern and western mountain passes are of major historical significance due to the religious data that the site offers, and its settlement history. This interest increased with the rise of awareness as to the threats that the 1965 approved master plan can induce. For this reason, the Ministry of culture took a decision on 9 January 1966 providing for the registration of the site on the following grounds:

Ten years after the implementation of the approved master plan, the ancient city and its constructional texture were exposed to clear damage. The rise of awareness as to the significance of the constructional texture and the specificities of the local community of the city of Maaloula urged authorities to review the first registration decision.

Pursuant to what precedes, and upon authorities' directives, the Ministry of culture issued the edict n° 243 /A on 30 September 1976 providing for the registration of the ancient city and its buildings as archeological sites and buildings.

3.3 Issues pertaining to archeological sites

The aforementioned caves face issues related to extensive neglect, and it is extremely rare to find one that does not require maintenance, restoration, and treatment of its surroundings. Despite the registration of these caves as archeological sites, the proposals formulated to use and upgrade them in accordance with the principles of safeguarding historical areas have not yet been implemented. Religious caves as well as those that had different other functions can be resurrected, and traditional uses can be revived, such as olive presses and grapes presses in winemaking, and any other functions that can give back life to these sites and preserve them from neglect.

1. Eastern pass

It is one of the archeological sites, and besides its spiritual and religious significance, its topography, its aquatic components and diversity of its ecosystem endow it with a touristic attractiveness, ranking on top of Maaloula sites. It suffers from lack of cleanliness and visual pollution resulting from applied inscriptions and colors on its body, as well as the dysfunction of its water stream and non treatment of its floor. Also, basic services are not supplied to the site, such as lighting and cleaning etc.

2. Western pass

This site is considered as one of the important archeological landscapes of Maaloula city. Besides its function as a major connection to the Monastery of Mar Sarkis, it is host to several outstanding historical sites like the court and the citadel. This pass has undergone extensive transformation within the urban plan implementation.

3.3 Infrastructure issues

Maaloula city, as is the case of several towns in Qalamoun, is confronted with the threat of non addressed sanitation pollution. The situation is exacerbated and growing more complicated as sanitation waste water flows towards the valley where high value orchards and agricultural fields are situated. It is preponderant that the failure of the sanitation system caused and is causing a regression in cultivable land in the area, besides a number of additional repercussions. In such zones, sanitation projects are prioritized by municipalities and are jointly examined with the neighboring towns.

3.4 Geological issues

Geological strata in Maaloula area:

Based on the Maaloula city special report, established by the General Establishment of Geology and Mineral Resources on the geological status of Maaloula town, and issued in January 2003, the following points are to be taken up:

1. Geodynamic threats in Maaloula represent a real danger, especially the fissured body above Monastery II, jeopardizing the safety of the monastery and the village.
2. The collapse of masses may cause human and material disasters and losses at any time and without prior notice, in the absence of any safety measure that can repel such an incident.
3. Construction of modern buildings down the fallen mass or in its proximity exposes it to danger.

Figure 2: Geological section of Maaloula village

Figure 3: Fissured, sliding and moving masses above the monastery

3.5 Issues regarding the safeguard of the flora

Cultivated land in Maaloula is subdivided into irrigated land and dry land. Irrigated land occurs at Lower Maaloula (Maaloula tahta), and was cultivated by its first inhabitants as graduating terraces, which were as attractive and agreeable as the houses, streets and pathways of Maaloula. Due to its appropriate and fertile soil, all types of cultures were practiced on the land, be it summer or winter cultivations, including the best kinds of wheat, yellow corn and fruit trees such as apricot, berries, peach, nuts, poplar, ashes and willow, using an efficient irrigating system, channeling water from the two springs gushing in the eastern and western mountain passes. Water was distributed via two meters on the Maalouli families and monasteries, which is still operational to date. Whereas dry land, which is vast and extended around Maaloula from all sides, relies on the scarce rainfall, as Maaloula is located outside the rain line. Previously, on dry lands, the cultures that were practiced included barley, beans, lenses and ervil, besides grapes, figs and sumac. Many water springs gush from these dry lands, including Souda spring, Taraya spring, Sharaya spring, and Bouqatha spring.

This flora started regressing considerably, although it constitutes the subject of human activity throughout the successive centuries; it also represents a consistent agricultural system, with all the handicraft activities related to it.

4. Strategies to safeguard these sites:

Many countries decided to rise from the level of protecting the borders of sites to preserving the contents, which encloses the protection of social, cultural and economic practices. The notion of the scene or landscape itself was perceived from a deeper perspective, incorporating the individual's view and the related feelings and reminiscences, combined with all his or her interests. The scenes before us today are a representation of how the natural void was slowly and gradually shaped throughout history, which required the elaboration of relevant laws and regulations.

We witness here a natural, environmental and economic consistency of natural and historical landscapes of Maaloula. Based on the resolution issued by the Hague Conference in its 12th session held in Paris on 11th December 1962, with respect to the safeguard of the beauty of natural landscapes and sites, and which is considered as a major directive on managing natural sites, it is required to bear an interest in preserving the beauty of natural landscapes and sites, whether they are natural or man-made, especially when they present a cultural and aesthetic significance, constituting parts of typical ecosystems. Here it is necessary to restore the initial conditions of those sites whenever that is possible.

This perspective gains utmost significance when those ecosystems are in danger of gradual degradation of their flora, or exposed to pollution and urban abusive expansion, or when the sites contain invaluable historical buildings.

For that reason, the conference, upon its examination of such sites, recommended the implementation of several measures, including the following:

1. Within the process of building general or special constructions on those sites, some aesthetic requirements have to be observed in harmony with the landscape, while refraining from superfluous imitation of some traditional models.
2. Reaffirming the necessity to divide and classify the natural site into zones according to significance and specificity.
3. The project should include provisions on the easement rights that should be defined to ensure the safeguard of the important parts of the site.
4. A study should be conducted to select construction materials, hues, lighting and aquatic areas, to ensure harmony.

The consideration of the conditions of these sites to guarantee their protection requires a number of measures, most of which are provided in international law and treaties, to achieve the following:

1. Definition of the objective behind protection;
2. To set up a graduated classification starting from groups (natural landscapes, village..) to isolated and individual items;
3. Delimitation of the nature of components as tangible or non tangible;
4. Establishing a distinction between protected components and endangered ones, and between special and normal components;
5. Distinction between living and neglected heritage, the latter being of no use today and threatens to ruin gradually or disappear, such as cultivated terraces, or handicrafts that should be transmitted over generations.

Regarding the safeguard mechanisms, endeavors and actions should converge, using geographic information systems, topographic surveying, combined with social, economic and historic surveys, in order to obtain scientific material conducive to finding solutions that are compatible with those natural scenes and landscapes.

5. Recommendations and outcomes:

Based on the project aiming at managing and upgrading the town of Maaloula in compliance with the relevant specifications that we have developed, a number of short term and long term strategies and policies have been identified, and several recommendations have been presented:

1. The necessity to collect accurate data and information on the site;
2. The necessity to suspend the implementation of the approved urban master plan;
3. Ensuring the supply of the town with urgent services (schools, health centers..);
4. Ensuring the protection and cleanliness of mountainous areas, of the eastern and western passes and archeological sites. The project is always under study, and we hope to reach solutions that are in conformity with the natural, historical and constructional value of Maaloula, which shall set the model for the neighboring towns;
5. Involvement of the local community in the process of elaborating safeguard policies;
6. Conducting profound geological studies to stabilize rocks in the city;

7. Non governmental entities should be installed to support the implementation of the safeguard measures;
8. New laws should provide that offenders are bound to pay compensation and restore the site to its initial condition;
9. Ensuring support to cultivation, and preservation of environment and water resources.